

Let $BCC(E)$ denote the set of all the set of all nonempty, bounded, closed and convex subsets of E . For more detail on multivalued maps see the books of Deimling [10], Hu and Papageorgiou [11].

An upper semicontinuous map $H : E \rightarrow E$ is said to be condensing if for any subset $B \subseteq E$ with $\alpha(B) \neq 0$, we have $\alpha(H(B)) < \alpha(B)$, where α denotes the Kuratowski measure of noncompactness. It is easy to see that a completely continuous multivalued map is a condensing map.

We say that a family $\{C(t) : t \in R\}$ of operators in $B(E)$ is a strongly continuous cosine family if

- (i) $C(0) = I$ (I is the identity operator in E),
- (ii) $C(t+s) + C(t-s) = 2C(t)C(s)$ for all $s, t \in R$,
- (iii) the map $t \mapsto C(t)x$ is strongly continuous for each $x \in E$.

The strongly continuous sine family $\{S(t) : t \in R\}$, associated to the given strongly continuous cosine family $\{C(t) : t \in R\}$, is defined by

$$S(t)x = \int_0^t C(s)x ds, \quad x \in E, \quad t \in R.$$

The infinitesimal generator $A : E \rightarrow E$ of a cosine family $\{C(t) : t \in R\}$ is defined by

$$Ax = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} C(t)x|_{t=0}.$$

For more details on strongly continuous cosine and sine families, we refer the reader to the books of Goldstein [12] and to the papers of Fattorini [13,14] and Travis and Webb [15,16].

The key tool in our approach is following fixed-point theorem.

Theorem 1(Martelli [9]). Let E be a Banach space and $N : E \rightarrow BCC(E)$ a condensing map. If the set

$$\Omega = \{x \in E : \lambda x \in Nx, \text{ for some } \lambda > 1\}$$

is bounded, then N has a fixed point.

III. MAIN RESULT

In the following, we shall apply Theorem 1 to study the existence of solution of system(1).

Definition 1. A function $x : (-\infty, b] \rightarrow H$ is called a mild solution of system(1) if the following holds: ϕ be \mathfrak{F}_0 measurable H -valued stochastic processes $x_0 = \phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$ on $(-\infty, 0]$ and the integral equation

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = C(t)\phi(0) + S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ \quad + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, x_s)ds \\ \quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \text{ for a.e. } t \in J, \\ x_0 = \phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h, \quad t \in J_0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

is satisfied, where

$$f \in S_{F,x} = \{f \in L^2(J, H) : f(t) \in F(t, x_t), \text{ for a.e. } t \in J\}.$$

To investigate the existence of solution of system (1), we use the following hypotheses:

(H₁) A is the infinitesimal generator of a strongly continuous and bounded cosine family $\{C(t) : t \in J\}$.

Assume that $C(t)$ is compact and there exists constant $M_1 > 0$ such that $M_1 = \sup\{|C(t)| : t \in J\}$.

(H₂) There exists constants $c_1 \geq 0$ and $c_2 \geq 0$ such that

$$E|g(t, u)|^p \leq c_1 \|u\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2, \quad t \in J, \quad u \in \mathfrak{B}_h.$$

(H₃) $F : J \times \mathfrak{B}_h \rightarrow BCC(H); (t, \phi) \rightarrow F(t, \phi)$ is measurable with respect to t for each $\phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$, Usc with respect to ϕ for each $t \in J$, and for each fixed $\phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$, the set

$$S_{F,\phi} = \{f \in L^2(J, H) : f(t) \in F(t, \phi), \text{ for a.e. } t \in J\}$$

is nonempty.

(H₄) The operator G with values $(G(x))(t) = g(t, x_t), t \in J$, G is completely continuous in $C(J, H)$ and for any bounded set $V \subseteq C(J, H)$, the set $\{t \rightarrow g(t, x_t) : x \in V\}$ is equicontinuous in $C(J, H)$.

(H₅) $E \|F(t, \phi)\|_2^p = \sup\{E \|v\|_2^p : v \in F(t, \phi)\} \leq p(t)\psi(\|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p), t \in J, p \in L^2(J, R^+), \phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$, and $\psi : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ is a continuous nondecreasing function, and the following inequality holds:

$$\int_0^b \bar{m}(s)ds < \int_N^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1+g(s)+\psi(g(s))} ds,$$

where

$$\bar{m}(t) = \max\{4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p c_1, 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p c_2, 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1}M_1^p p(t)\}$$

$$g(s) = (ls^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p, l = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s)ds < +\infty,$$

$$N = 4^{p-1}M_1^p E|\phi(0)|^p + 8^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (E|\eta|^p + c_1\|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2).$$

Lemma 1(Lasota and Opial[17]). Let I be a compact real interval and E be a Banach space. Let F be a multivalued map satisfying (H₃) and let Γ be a linear continuous mapping from $L^2(I, E) \rightarrow C(I, E)$. Then the operator

$$\Gamma \circ S_F : C(I, E) \rightarrow BCC(C(I, E)),$$

$$x \rightarrow (\Gamma \circ S_F)(x) = \Gamma(S_{F,x})$$

is a closed graph operator in $C(I, E) \times C(I, E)$.

$C(J_1, H)$ is the space of all continuous H -valued stochastic processes $\{\xi(t) : t \in J_1\}$. Now we consider the space \mathfrak{B}_b , let $\mathfrak{B}_b = \{x : x \in C((-\infty, b], H), x_0 = \phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h\}$, Let $\|\cdot\|$ be a seminorm in \mathfrak{B}_b defined by

$$\|x\|_b = \|x_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} + \sup_{s \in [0, b]} (E|x(s)|^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad x \in \mathfrak{B}_b.$$

Lemma 2. Suppose $x \in \mathfrak{B}_b$, then for $t \in J, x_t \in \mathfrak{B}_h$. Moreover

$$LE^{\frac{1}{p}}|x(t)|^p \leq \|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \leq l \sup_{s \in [0, t]} (E|x(s)|^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|x_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h},$$

where $l = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s)ds < +\infty$.

Proof: For any $t \in [0, a]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} &= \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_t(\theta)|^p ds \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{-t} h(s) \sup_{\theta \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_t(\theta)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + \int_{-t}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_t(\theta)|^p ds \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{-t} h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [t+s, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + \int_{-t}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [t+s, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\leq \int_{-\infty}^{-t} h(s) \left[\sup_{\theta_1 \in [t+s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sup_{\theta_1 \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p \right] ds \\
 &\quad + \int_{-t}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{-t} h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [t+s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + \int_{-t}^0 h(s) ds \times \sup_{\theta_1 \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p \\
 &\leq \int_{-\infty}^{-t} h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + l \sup_{\theta_1 \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p \\
 &\leq \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + l \sup_{s \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(s)|^p \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta_1 \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_0(\theta_1)|^p ds \\
 &\quad + l \sup_{s \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(s)|^p \\
 &= l \sup_{s \in [0, t]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(s)|^p + \|x_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $\phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$, then $x_t \in \mathfrak{B}_h$. Moreover

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} &= \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) \sup_{\theta \in [s, 0]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_t(\theta)|^p ds \\
 &\geq E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x_t(0)|^p \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) ds = l E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(t)|^p.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is complete.

Now, consider the multivalued map $\mathfrak{L} : \mathfrak{B}_b \rightarrow 2^{\mathfrak{B}_b}$ defined by $\mathfrak{L}x$ the set of $\rho \in \mathfrak{B}_b$ such that

$$\rho(t) = \begin{cases} \phi(t), & t \in (-\infty, 0], \\ C(t)\phi(0) + S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, x_s) ds \\ \quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), & t \in J, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $f \in S_{F, x}$.

We shall show that the operator \mathfrak{L} has fixed points, which are then a solution of system (1). For $\phi \in \mathfrak{B}_h$, we define $\bar{\phi}$ by

$$\bar{\phi}(t) = \begin{cases} \phi(t), & -\infty < t \leq 0 \\ C(t)\phi(0), & 0 \leq t \leq b \end{cases}$$

then $\bar{\phi} \in \mathfrak{B}_b$. Set

$$x(t) = y(t) + \bar{\phi}(t), \quad -\infty < t \leq b.$$

It is clear to see that x satisfies (2) if and only if y satisfies $y_0 = 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(t) &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\
 &\quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\mathfrak{B}_b^0 = \{y \in \mathfrak{B}_b : y_0 = 0 \in \mathfrak{B}_h\}$. For any $y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0$,

$$\|y\|_b = \|y_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} + \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |y(s)|^p = \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |y(s)|^p.$$

Thus $(\mathfrak{B}_b^0, \|\cdot\|_b)$ is a Banach space. Set $\mathfrak{B}_q = \{y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0 : \|y\|_b \leq q\}$ for some $q \geq 0$, then $\mathfrak{B}_q \subseteq \mathfrak{B}_b^0$ is uniformly bounded, for any $y \in \mathfrak{B}_q$, from Lemma 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|y_t + \bar{\phi}_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} &\leq \|y_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} + \|\bar{\phi}_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \\
 &\leq l \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |y(s)|^p + \|y_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \\
 &\quad + l \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |\bar{\phi}(s)|^p + \|\bar{\phi}_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \\
 &\leq lq + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} + l \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} |C(s)| E^{\frac{1}{p}} |\phi(0)|^p \\
 &\leq l(q + M_1 E^{\frac{1}{p}} |\phi(0)|^p) + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} = q'.
 \end{aligned}$$

Define the multivalued map $\mathfrak{L}_1 : \mathfrak{B}_b^0 \rightarrow 2^{\mathfrak{B}_b^0}$ defined by $\mathfrak{L}_1 y$ the set of $\bar{\rho} \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0$ such that

$$\bar{\rho}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t \in (-\infty, 0], \\ S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ \quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), & t \in J. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Lemma 3. If the hypotheses $(H_1) - (H_5)$ satisfied, then $\mathfrak{L}_1 : \mathfrak{B}_b^0 \rightarrow 2^{\mathfrak{B}_b^0}$ is a completely continuous multivalued map, \mathfrak{L}_1 with a convex closed value.

Proof. We divide the proof into several steps.

Step 1. $\mathfrak{L}_1 y$ is convex for each $y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0$.

In fact, if $\bar{\rho}_1, \bar{\rho}_2$ belong to $\mathfrak{L}_1 y$, then there exist $f_1, f_2 \in S_{F, y}$ such that for each $t \in J$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\rho}_i(t) &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\
 &\quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f_i(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J, \quad i = 1, 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\lambda \bar{\rho}_1 + (1 - \lambda) \bar{\rho}_2)(t) \\
 &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\
 &\quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)(\lambda f_1(s) + (1 - \lambda) f_2(s)) dw(s).
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $S_{F,y}$ is convex, we have $\lambda\bar{\rho}_1 + (1-\lambda)\bar{\rho}_2 \in \mathcal{L}_1 y$.

Step 2. \mathcal{L}_1 maps bounded set into bounded set in \mathfrak{B}_b^0 . Indeed, it is enough to show that there exists a positive constant Λ such that for each $\bar{\rho} \in \mathcal{L}_1 y$, $y \in \mathfrak{B}_q = \{y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0 : \|y\|_b \leq q\}$ one has $\|\bar{\rho}\|_{b \leq \Lambda}$. If $\bar{\rho} \in \mathcal{L}_1 y$, then there exist $f \in S_{F,y}$, such that for each $t \in J$,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\rho}(t) &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds \\ &\quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J. \end{aligned}$$

By $(H_1) - (H_4)$ we have for $t \in J$,

$$\begin{aligned} &E|\bar{\rho}(t)|^p \\ &= E|S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds \\ &\quad + \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s)|^p \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}E|S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)]|^p \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}E|\int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds|^p \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}E|\int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s)|_2^p \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p + 2^{p-1}E|g(0, \phi)|^p) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}b^{p-1} \int_0^t E|C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}E\{\int_0^t [|S(t-s)|^p \|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}}\} \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p + 2^{p-1}(c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1 \|y_s + \bar{\phi}_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2) ds \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}(M_1 b)^p \{ \int_0^t [E\|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}} \} \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p + 2^{p-1}(c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1 q^p + c_2) ds \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}(M_1 b)^p \sup_{x \in [0, q']} \psi(x^p) \{ \int_0^t (p(s))^{\frac{2}{p}} ds \}^{\frac{p}{2}} \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p + 2^{p-1}(c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}b^p M_1^p (c_1 q^p + c_2) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}(M_1 b)^p \sup_{x \in [0, q']} \psi(x^p) t^{\frac{p}{2}-1} \int_0^t p(s) ds \\ &\leq 3^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p + 2^{p-1}(c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}b^p M_1^p (c_1 q^p + c_2) \\ &\quad + 3^{p-1}(M_1 b)^p \sup_{x \in [0, q']} \psi(x^p) b^{\frac{p}{2}-1} \int_0^b p(s) ds \\ &= \Lambda^p. \end{aligned}$$

then for each $\bar{\rho} \in \mathcal{L}_1(\mathfrak{B}_q)$, we have

$$\|\bar{\rho}\|_{b \leq \Lambda}.$$

Step 3. \mathcal{L}_1 maps bounded sets into equicontinuous sets of \mathfrak{B}_b^0 . Let $0 < t_1 < t_2 \leq b$, for each $y \in \mathfrak{B}_q = \{y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0 : \|y\|_b \leq q\}$ and $\bar{\rho} \in \mathcal{L}_1 y$, there exists $f \in S_{F,y}$ such that (4). Thus

$$\begin{aligned} &E|\bar{\rho}(t_2) - \bar{\rho}(t_1)|^p \\ &= E|(S(t_2) - S(t_1))[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ &\quad + \int_0^{t_1} [C(t_2-s) - C(t_1-s)]g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds \\ &\quad + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} C(t_2-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds \\ &\quad + \int_0^{t_1} [S(t_2-s) - S(t_1-s)]f(s)dw(s) \\ &\quad + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} S(t_2-s)f(s)dw(s)|^p \\ &\leq 5^{p-1}E|[S(t_2) - S(t_1)][\eta - g(0, \phi)]|^p \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E|\int_0^{t_1} [C(t_2-s) - C(t_1-s)]g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds|^p \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E|\int_{t_1}^{t_2} C(t_2-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)ds|^p \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E|\int_0^{t_1} [S(t_2-s) - S(t_1-s)]f(s)dw(s)|_2^p \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E|\int_{t_1}^{t_2} S(t_2-s)f(s)dw(s)|_2^p \\ &\leq 5^{p-1}|S(t_2) - S(t_1)|^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p \\ &\quad + 2^{p-1}c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + 2^{p-1}c_2) \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}b^{p-1} \int_0^{t_1} |C(t_2-s) - C(t_1-s)|^p \\ &\quad E|g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}(t_2 - t_1)^{p-1} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |C(t_2-s)|^p E|g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E\{\int_0^{t_1} [|S(t_2-s) - S(t_1-s)|^p \|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}}\} \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}E\{\int_{t_1}^{t_2} [|S(t_2-s)|^p \|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}}\} \\ &\leq 5^{p-1}|S(t_2) - S(t_1)|^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p \\ &\quad + 2^{p-1}c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + 2^{p-1}c_2) \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}b^{p-1} \int_0^{t_1} |C(t_2-s) - C(t_1-s)|^p \\ &\quad (c_1 \|y_s + \bar{\phi}_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2) ds \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}(t_2 - t_1)^{p-1} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |C(t_2-s)|^p \\ &\quad (c_1 \|y_s + \bar{\phi}_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2) ds \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}\{\int_0^{t_1} [|S(t_2-s) - S(t_1-s)|^p E\|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}}\} \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}\{\int_{t_1}^{t_2} [|S(t_2-s)|^p E\|f(s)\|_2^{\frac{2}{p}} ds]^{\frac{p}{2}}\} \\ &\leq 5^{p-1}|S(t_2) - S(t_1)|^p (2^{p-1}E|\eta|^p \\ &\quad + 2^{p-1}c_1 \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + 2^{p-1}c_2) \\ &\quad + 5^{p-1}b^{p-1} \int_0^{t_1} |C(t_2-s) - C(t_1-s)|^p \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (c_1 \|y_s + \bar{\phi}_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_n}^p + c_2) ds \\ & + 5^{p-1} (t_2 - t_1)^{p-1} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |C(t_2 - s)|^p \\ & (c_1 \|y_s + \bar{\phi}_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_n}^p + c_2) ds \\ & + 5^{p-1} b^{\frac{p}{2}-1} \int_0^{t_1} |S(t_2 - s) - S(t_1 - s)|^p E \|f(s)\|_2^p ds \\ & + 5^{p-1} (t_2 - t_1)^{\frac{p}{2}-1} \int_{t_2}^{t_1} |S(t_2 - s)|^p E \|f(s)\|_2^p ds \end{aligned}$$

The right-hand side of inequality above is independent of $y \in \mathfrak{B}_q$ and tends to zero as $t_2 \rightarrow t_1$. Thus the set $\{\mathfrak{L}_1 y : y \in \mathfrak{B}_q\}$ is equicontinuous. (Note that we considered here only the case $0 < t_1 < t_2 \leq b$, since the other case $t_1 < t_2 \leq 0$ or $t_1 \leq 0 \leq t_2 \leq b$ are very simple). As a consequence of the Ascoli-Arzelà theorem, it suffice to show that \mathfrak{L}_1 maps \mathfrak{B}_q into a precompact set in H . Let $0 < t \leq b$ be fixed and let ϵ be a real number satisfying $0 < \epsilon < t$. For $y \in \mathfrak{B}_q$ we define

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\rho}_\epsilon(t) &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^{t-\epsilon} C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ &+ \int_0^{t-\epsilon} S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J. \end{aligned}$$

since $C(t)$ and $S(t)$ is compact operators, the set $H_\epsilon(t) = \{\bar{\rho}_\epsilon(t) : \bar{\rho}_\epsilon \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y\}$ is precompact in H for every $\epsilon, 0 < \epsilon < t$. Moreover, for every $\bar{\rho} \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & E|\bar{\rho}_\epsilon(t) - \bar{\rho}(t)|^p \\ & \leq 2^{p-1} E \left| \int_{t-\epsilon}^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \right|^p \\ & + 2^{p-1} E \left\| \int_{t-\epsilon}^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s) \right\|_2^p \\ & \leq 2^{p-1} \epsilon^{p-1} \int_{t-\epsilon}^t E|C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ & + 2^{p-1} E \left\{ \int_{t-\epsilon}^t [|S(t-s)|^p \|f(s)\|_2^p] ds \right\}^{\frac{p}{2}} \\ & \leq 2^{p-1} \epsilon^{p-1} \int_{t-\epsilon}^t |C(t-s)|^p E|g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ & + 2^{p-1} \left\{ \int_{t-\epsilon}^t [|S(t-s)|^p E\|f(s)\|_2^p] ds \right\}^{\frac{p}{2}} \\ & \leq 2^{p-1} \epsilon^{p-1} \int_{t-\epsilon}^t |C(t-s)|^p E|g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s)|^p ds \\ & + 2^{p-1} \epsilon^{\frac{p}{2}-1} \left\{ \int_{t-\epsilon}^t |S(t-s)|^p E\|f(s)\|_2^p ds \right\}^{\frac{p}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore there are precompact sets arbitrarily close to the set $\{\bar{\rho}(t) : \bar{\rho} \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y\}$. So the set $\{\bar{\rho}(t) : \bar{\rho} \in \mathfrak{L}_1 \mathfrak{B}_q\}$ is precompact in H . Hence, the operator \mathfrak{L}_1 is completely continuous.

Step 4. \mathfrak{L}_1 has a closed graph.

Let $y^{(n)} \rightarrow y^*$, $\bar{\rho}_n \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y^{(n)}$ and $\bar{\rho}_n \rightarrow \bar{\rho}_*$. We shall prove that $\bar{\rho}_* \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y^*$. Indeed, $\bar{\rho}_n \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y^{(n)}$ means that there exists

$f_n \in S_{F, y^{(n)}}$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{\rho}_n(t) \\ &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^{(n)} + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ &+ \int_0^t S(t-s)f_n(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J. \end{aligned}$$

We must prove that there exists $f_* \in S_{F, y^*}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{\rho}_*(t) \\ &= S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] + \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^* + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ &+ \int_0^t S(t-s)f_*(s)dw(s), \quad t \in J. \end{aligned}$$

since g is continuous, for $t \in J$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \|\{\bar{\rho}_n(t) - S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ & - \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^{(n)} + \bar{\phi}_s) ds\} - \{\bar{\rho}_*(t) \\ & - S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] - \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^* + \bar{\phi}_s) ds\}\| \\ & \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Consider the linear continuous operator

$$\Gamma : L^p(J, H) \rightarrow C(J, H),$$

$$f \rightarrow \Gamma(f)(t) = \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s).$$

From Lemma 1, it follows that $\Gamma \circ S_F$ is a closed graph. Moreover, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{\rho}_n(t) - S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ & - \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^{(n)} + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \in \Gamma(S_{F, y^{(n)}}). \end{aligned}$$

Since $y^{(n)} \rightarrow y^*$, it follows from Lemma 1 that

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{\rho}_*(t) - S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] - \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s^* + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ &= \int_0^t S(t-s)f_*(s)dw(s). \end{aligned}$$

for some $f_* \in S_{F, y^*}$.

Therefore \mathfrak{L}_1 is a completely continuous multivalued map, Usc with convex closed values.

Now, in order to apply Theorem 1, we introduce a parameter $\lambda > 1$ and consider the following auxiliary problems:

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = C(t)\phi(0) + \frac{1}{\lambda} S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ \quad + \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, x_s) ds \\ \quad + \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \quad \text{for a.e } t \in J, \\ x(t) = \phi(t), \quad t \in (-\infty, 0], \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $f \in S_{F, x}$.

Lemma 4. If hypotheses $(H_1) - (H_5)$ are satisfied. Let $x(t)$ be a mild solution of system (5), then there exists a priori bounds $R > 0$, such that $\|x_t\| \leq R$, $t \in J$, where R depends only on b and the function $\psi(\cdot)$ and $p(\cdot)$.

Proof. From the system (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & E|x(t)|^p \\ \leq & 4^{p-1}E|C(t)\phi(0)|^p + 4^{p-1}E|S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)]|^p \\ & + 4^{p-1}E\left|\int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, x_s)ds\right|^p \\ & + 4^{p-1}E\left|\int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s)\right|^p \\ \leq & 4^{p-1}|C(t)|^p E|\phi(0)|^p \\ & + 4^{p-1}|S(t)|^p \{2^{p-1}(E|\eta|^p + E|g(0, \phi)|^p)\} \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{p-1}\int_0^t |C(t-s)|^p E|g(s, x_s)|^p ds \\ & + 4^{p-1}\left\{\int_0^t [|S(t-s)|^p E\|f(S)\|_2^2 ds]\right\}^{\frac{p}{2}} \\ \leq & 4^{p-1}M_1^p E|\phi(0)|^p + 8^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (E|\eta|^p \\ & + c_1\|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2) \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)ds \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}\int_0^t |S(t-s)|^p E\|f(s)\|_2^p ds \\ \leq & 4^{p-1}M_1^p E|\phi(0)|^p + 8^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (E|\eta|^p \\ & + c_1\|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2) \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)ds \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p b^p \int_0^t p(s)\psi(\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p)ds \\ = & N + 4^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)ds \\ & + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p b^p \int_0^t p(s)\psi(\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p)ds, \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} N = & 4^{p-1}M_1^p E|\phi(0)|^p + 8^{p-1}M_1^p b^p (E|\eta|^p \\ & + c_1\|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2). \end{aligned}$$

Thus from Lemma 2, it follows

$$\begin{aligned} \|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} & \leq l \sup_{s \in [0, t]} [E|x(s)|^p]^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|x_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \\ & \leq l[N + 4^{p-1}b^{p-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p + c_2)ds \\ & \quad + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p b^p \int_0^t p(s)\psi(\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}^p)ds]^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\mu(t) = \sup\{\|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} : 0 \leq s \leq t\}$, then the function $\mu(t)$

is nondecreasing in J , and we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(t) & \leq l[4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\mu^p(s) + c_2)ds \\ & \quad + 4^{p-1}M_1^p b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1} \int_0^t p(s)\psi(\mu^p(s))ds + N]^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\alpha(t) = 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p \int_0^t (c_1\mu^p(s) + c_2)ds + 4^{p-1}M_1^p b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1} \int_0^t p(s)\psi(\mu^p(s))ds + N$, so we have

$$\alpha(0) = N, \quad \mu(t) \leq l(\alpha(t))^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}, \quad t \in J,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'(t) & = 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p (c_1\mu^p(t) + c_2) \\ & \quad + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1}M_1^p p(t)\psi(\mu^p(t)) \\ & \leq 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p (c_1(l(\alpha(t))^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p + c_2) \\ & \quad + 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1}M_1^p p(t)\psi(l((\alpha(t))^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p) \\ & \leq \bar{m}(t)(1 + (l(\alpha(t))^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p \\ & \quad + \psi((l(\alpha(t))^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p)) \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{m}(t) = & \max\{4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p c_1, 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{p}{2}-1}M_1^p c_2, \\ & 4^{p-1}b^{\frac{3p}{2}-1}M_1^p p(t)\}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\frac{\alpha'(t)}{1 + g(\alpha(t)) + \psi(g(\alpha(t)))} \leq \bar{m}(t),$$

and

$$\int_0^t \frac{\alpha'(s)}{1 + g(\alpha(s)) + \psi(g(\alpha(s)))} ds \leq \int_0^t \bar{m}(s)ds,$$

That is

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\alpha(0)}^{\alpha(t)} \frac{1}{1 + g(s) + \psi(g(s))} ds & \leq \int_0^t \bar{m}(s)ds \\ & < \int_N^{+\infty} \frac{1}{1 + g(s) + \psi(g(s))} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\alpha(0) = N$, $g(s) = (ls^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h})^p$. This inequality implies there is a constant \bar{k} such that $\alpha(t) \leq \bar{k}$ for every $t \in [0, b]$, hence

$$\|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \leq \mu(t) \leq l[\alpha(t)]^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \leq l\bar{k}^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h}.$$

This shows that exist constant $R = l\bar{k}^{\frac{1}{p}} + \|\phi\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} > 0$, such that $\|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \leq R$.

Theorem 2 Assume that hypotheses $(H_1) - (H_5)$ hold, then system (1) has at least one mild solution on J_1 .

Proof Let $\Omega = \{y \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0 : \lambda y \in \mathfrak{L}_1 y, \text{ for some } \lambda > 1\}$. Then for any $y \in \Omega$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \frac{1}{\lambda} S(t)[\eta - g(0, \phi)] \\ &+ \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^t C(t-s)g(s, y_s + \bar{\phi}_s) ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^t S(t-s)f(s)dw(s), \end{aligned}$$

which implies the function $x = y + \bar{\phi}$ is a mild solution of system (5), for which we have proved in Lemma 4 that $\|x_t\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} \leq R, t \in J$, and hence from Lemma 2

$$\begin{aligned} \|y\|_b &= \|y_0\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} + \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |y(s)|^p \\ &= \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |y(s)|^p \\ &\leq \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |x(s)|^p + \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |\bar{\phi}(s)|^p \\ &\leq \sup\{l^{-1} \|x_s\|_{\mathfrak{B}_h} : s \in [0, b]\} \\ &\quad + \sup_{s \in [0, b]} E^{\frac{1}{p}} |C(t)\phi(0)|^p \\ &\leq l^{-1}R + M_1 E^{\frac{1}{p}} |\phi(0)|^p, \end{aligned}$$

which implies Ω is bounded on J .

Hence, it follows from Lemma 4 and Theorem 1 that the operator \mathfrak{L}_1 has a fixed point $y^* \in \mathfrak{B}_b^0$. Let $x(t) = y^*(t) + \bar{\phi}(t), t \in (-\infty, b]$. Then x is a fixed point of the operator \mathfrak{L} which is a mild solution of problem (1).

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